

STUDIES IN ELBS PERSULPHATE OXIDATION. PART III. FURTHER
OXIDATIONS IN THE COUMARIN SERIES AND OXIDATION
OF 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE

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IN continuation of the work described in previous parts, 5-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin, 4:6-dimethylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid have been successfully oxidised, and the hitherto unknown 5:6-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, 8-hydroxy-4:6-dimethylcoumarin and 5:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid synthesised. The natural coumarin, fraxinol, and 5:8-dihydroxyquinoline, which were previously synthesised by other methods, have now been synthesised by the oxidation of 5:7-dimethoxycoumarin and 8-hydroxyquinoline respectively. This method has been applied for the first time to a nitrogenous heterocyclic compound. The oxidation of 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin resulted in the formation of a pasty uncrystallisable mass and the oxidation of 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-, and 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin resulted in the formation of complex compounds with high and indefinite melting points.

In continuation of the work described in Part I (Parikh and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 369) the applicability of this reaction to the synthesis of new coumarin derivatives has been studied further. Of the six possible dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin derivatives, with both the hydroxy groups in the benzenoid part, 5:7-dihydroxy-, 6:7-dihydroxy- and 7:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarins are known (Pechmann and Cohen, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187; Pechmann and Kraft, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 421; Pechmann and Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119, respectively).

The remaining three, 5:6-dihydroxy-, 5:8-dihydroxy- and 6:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarins are unknown. Of these, the 5:6 dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has now been synthesised.

5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin has been oxidised with potassium persulphate after dissolving it in warm alkali which presumably opens the α -pyrone ring as shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and the 5-methoxy-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, so obtained, demethylated to 5:6-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.

8-Methoxycoumarin has been successfully oxidised to 6-hydroxy-8-methoxycoumarin by Mauthner (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 152, 23) and so for the synthesis of 6:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, δ -methoxy-4-methylcoumarin would be the most suitable starting material, but this coumarin has so far not been prepared. Attempts to prepare it by the condensation of catechol with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid, anhydrous aluminium chloride or zinc chloride did not succeed. Guaiacol also did not condense with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid or zinc chloride. The alternative for the synthesis of 6:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was to oxidise 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin and to see if the oxidation could take place in the position *ortho* to the free hydroxyl group formed as a result of the opening of the α -pyrone ring. This, however, did not succeed; a pasty unworkable product was obtained. In this connection it was thought of interest to study the oxidation of another coumarin in which the 6-position was blocked by a substituent

and so 4:6-dimethylcoumarin was subjected to this oxidation when a product was obtained in extremely poor yield to which the structure of 8-hydroxy-4:6-dimethylcoumarin was assigned. These results are in keeping with the observations made by previous workers (Baker and Brown, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 2303) that where the *p*-position to the hydroxyl group in the phenol is occupied, oxidation takes place in the *ortho* position, but the yields are extremely poor.

The oxidation of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was next tried to see if the 8-position, which is *para* to the hydroxyl group in position '5', were selectively attacked and the desired 5:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin could be obtained. It was, however, found that a complex product with a high and indefinite m.p. was obtained. With a view to finding out whether the formation of such a product was specific of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin or was a general reaction of 5-hydroxycoumarins, the oxidation of 5-hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin was carried out when also a complex product with indefinite m.p. was obtained. The formation of these complex products may probably be due to oxidative coupling at 6-position. The oxidation of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was therefore next tried when an acid was obtained in very poor yield to which the structure of 5:8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was assigned. The decarboxylation of this product by the quinoline copper powder method or by heating in a sealed tube with water did not succeed.

5:7-Dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin has been previously oxidised successfully to 6-hydroxy-5:7-dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin *i.e.* 4-methylfraxinol (Parikh and Sethna, *loc. cit.*). The synthesis of the natural coumarin, fraxinol (5:7-dimethoxy-6-hydroxycoumarin) has now been conveniently carried out by the oxidation of 5:7-dimethoxycoumarin with potassium persulphate. Fraxinol has been previously synthesised by Späth and Jerzmanowska-Sienkiewiczowa (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 698) by Perkin's reaction on 2:4-dimethoxy-3:6-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, the starting material for this synthesis being pyrogallol trimethyl ether.

As a result of the successful application of this method of oxidation in the field of benzopyrones, it was thought of interest to study it in the case of other heterocyclic compounds. This method has so far not been applied to nitrogenous heterocyclic compounds and so the easily available 8-hydroxyquinoline was selected for this study. 8-Hydroxyquinoline has now been oxidised by this method to the known 5:8-dihydroxyquinoline in poor yield.

Fischer and Renouf (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1645) claimed to have obtained this compound by the reduction of quinoline quinone in alcoholic solution with sulphurous acid. According to these authors it decomposes in aqueous solution on heating with the formation of a brown amorphous mass. Claus and Posselt (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1890, *ii*, 41, 32) claimed to have prepared it by fusing 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with potash above 250°, but it was stated to have decomposed without melting above 270°. Matsumura and Sone (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1406) have obtained 5:8-dihydroxyquinoline in good yield by reducing 5-nitroso-8-hydroxyquinoline with iron powder and hydrochloric acid and they give its m.p. as 181-83°. 5:8-Dihydroxyquinoline obtained in the present work gives the same melting point. On account of the ease with which the compound is transformed to a brown amorphous product

on heating with water, the usual procedure of working up the reaction product has to be modified, as shown in the experimental.

Very recently, Bhavsar and Desai (*Curr. Sci.*, 1950, 19, 312) have published a note on the nuclear oxidation of coumarins in which they list the coumarin derivatives they have oxidised. Fraxinol is one of the compounds obtained in this work, but as our work on the synthesis of fraxinol is a continuation of that described in Part I, and as it was completed before the above note appeared, we have included the same in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxidation of 5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin: 5-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228) (4.7 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5 g. in 50 c.c. water) by heating on a steam-bath for about half an hour. The solution was then cooled and potassium persulphate (7.5 g. in 150 c.c. of water) added gradually from a separating funnel during 3 hours. The solution was mechanically stirred and the temperature was not allowed to rise above 10°. After the addition was complete the reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour more and left overnight. The next day it was just acidified and extracted with ether twice. The ether extract gave negligible quantity of the starting material. Excess of hydrochloric acid (conc., 100 c.c.) was then added to the aqueous layer and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for half an hour. The solid which separated during heating was filtered after cooling the solution. More product was obtained on extraction of the filtrate with ether. The combined solids were crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles (2.3 g.), m. p. 186–88°. (Found: C, 64.3; H, 4.6. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires, C, 64.1; H, 4.8 per cent). The substance dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution to give a yellow solution.

5:6-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—5-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 5 c.c.) added. The mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath between 130° and 140° for 2 hours. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in sodium bisulphite solution was crystallised from rectified spirit in yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 248–49°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 4.4. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.2 per cent). The substance gives a green colour with alcoholic-ferric chloride and dissolves with deep red colour in sodium hydroxide solution.

5:6-Dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin, prepared by methylating the above coumarin with methyl iodide in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone solution, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles, m.p. 126–28°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 5.5. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.4 per cent).

Oxidation of 4:6-Dimethylcoumarin: 8-Hydroxy-4:6-dimethylcoumarin.—4:6-Dimethylcoumarin (Pechmann and Duisberg, *loc. cit.*) (5.2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 60 c.c.) by heating on a steam-bath for about half an hour and the cooled solution oxidised by the action of potassium persulphate solution (8.1 g. in 160 c.c. water). The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product

(3 g.) which came down on just acidifying the solution was found to be the original product. On heating with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid the oxidation product was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol in small colorless needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 214-16°. (Found : C, 69.6 ; H, 4.7. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5 ; H, 5.3 per cent).

Oxidation of 5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid : 5:8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—To 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*) (2.2 g.) sodium hydroxide solution (2 g. in 20 c.c. water) was added. The acid formed an insoluble sodium salt which dissolved during the subsequent addition of aqueous solution of potassium persulphate. To the above suspension of sodium salt, potassium persulphate (3 g. in 60 c.c. water) was added with mechanical stirring. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual on the next day. The product (1.1 g.) which came down on just acidifying the solution with hydrochloric acid was found to be the starting material. The product obtained on heating with excess of hydrochloric acid was crystallised (charcoal) from rectified spirit in tiny yellow needles (0.2 g.), m. p. 273-75° (efferv.). (Found : C, 55.8 ; H, 3.2. $C_{11}H_8O_6$ requires C, 55.9 ; H, 3.4 per cent). The acid dissolves in alkali to give a red solution and gives a blue colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Fraxinol (5:7-Dimethoxy-6-hydroxycoumarin).—5:7-Dimethoxycoumarin (Heyes and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1831) (2.0 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 20 c.c.) by heating on a steam-bath for an hour. The solution was cooled externally and oxidised as before with potassium persulphate (2.7 g. in 50 c.c. water). Next day the reaction mixture was made just acidic with hydrochloric acid and the unreacted original product (0.4 g.) which separated out was filtered. The product obtained on heating with excess of hydrochloric acid (conc., 30 c.c.) for an hour on a steam-bath was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in faint yellow, glistening needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 171-72°. (Found : C, 59.5 ; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$: C, 59.5 ; H, 4.5 per cent). It dissolves in alkali to give a deep yellow solution. Späth *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 140-41°. (Found : C, 59.2 ; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$: C, 59.1 ; H, 4.5 per cent). Späth *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

Oxidation of 8-Hydroxyquinoline : 5:8-Dihydroxyquinoline.—8-Hydroxyquinoline (2.9 g.) was mixed with sodium hydroxide solution (4 g. in 120 c.c. water). The insoluble sodium salt was formed. To this suspension a solution of potassium persulphate (5.4 g. in 100 c.c. water) was added gradually during 3 hours with mechanical stirring and external cooling. The clear dark red solution obtained was then kept for 36 hours in a stoppered flask in a frigidaire. Hydrochloric acid was then added to make the solution just acidic and the dark brown product (0.3 g.) which separated was filtered. This product had a very high and indefinite melting point. The filtrate was extracted with ether. The ether extract gave the starting substance (0.5 g.). Excess of hydrochloric acid (conc., 50 c.c.) was then added to the solution and it was kept overnight in a stoppered flask. A reddish crystalline solid (1 g.) separated which gave test for sulphur but not for chlorine. This therefore must be the intermediate

quinolyl potassium sulphate derivative. This solid was heated on a steam-bath with hydrochloric acid (conc., 30 c.c.) for an hour. The solid went in solution and on cooling deposited orange-yellow needles (0.7 g.). This was the hydrochloride. It did not melt till 300° but melted on heating on a spatula. If the reaction mixture is heated directly with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the intermediate potassium sulphate derivative not isolated, a brown amorphous product of high and indefinite melting point is obtained. The hydrochloride was filtered and decomposed with cold sodium bicarbonate solution. The 5:8-dihydroxyquinoline which separated was crystallised from benzene in colorless glistening needles (0.2 g.), m.p. $181-83^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 4.1; N, 8.8. Calc. for $C_7H_7O_2N$: C, 67.1; H, 4.4; N, 8.7 per cent). Matsumura and Sone (*loc. cit.*) also give the same m.p. The product gives a dark brown coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and an orange solution with sodium hydroxide. The final stage of decomposition should be carried out as quickly as possible and in a closed vessel as the solution immediately starts turning brown.

Further work is in progress.

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